

Supporting Information

Figure S1: Representative ^1H NMR spectra of unmodified gelatin and GelMA. Highlighted regions were used for calculating DoM, with; purple aromatic amino acids resonances (7.1-7.5 ppm) that are not chemically modified; blue methacrylate vinyl groups that appear after reaction (5.3-5.6 ppm), and; green lysine amino acids (2.9-3.0 ppm).

Figure S2: Quantification of GelMA hydrogel pore size. (A) Pore size of GelMA hydrogels calculated from SEM images. (B) Results of 2-way ANOVA with Tukey's multiple comparison test comparing pore sizes in different hydrogels. Results are displayed as mean \pm SEM of 41-206 measured pores from each hydrogel sample. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, **** $p < 0.0001$.

Figure S3: Representative amplitude sweep showing storage (G') and loss (G'') moduli measured at 1 Hz and strain increasing from 0.01% to 100% at 37°C to determine the linear viscoelastic region (LVR) to be applied for subsequent frequency sweep measurements.